

IMPROVEMENT OF BANKING COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND THEIR APPEARANCE IN UZBEKISTAN

Nizomova Mehrangiz Jamaliddinza

Denov Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

4-year student of banking

E-mail: nizomovamehrangiz@gmail.com

Abstract: This article explains the bank and customer communication channels, their types, ways of development, and the essence of the content. The current situation in Uzbekistan is explained in detail.

Keywords: communication channels, live chat, chatbot, call center, e-mail, social networks.

Introduction. Bank communication is the regular collection of information from customers to determine their complaints, attitudes, perceptions and suggestions, in addition, it includes the regular transfer of information by banks for various purposes to consider customer offers¹. Traditional means by which banks communicate with their customers include advertising, sales promotion, advertising, public relations, and personal selling². Today's customers expect more sensitive, active and faster communication with the bank. The traditional one-way communication of banks with customers is outdated; the bank should analyze

¹ Khadka K, Maharjan S. Customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Master in Business Mgmt. thesis, Dept. of Mgmt., Centria University of Applied Sciences, Pietarsaari, Finland; 2017.

² Kotler P, Armstrong G. Marketing tamoyillari. 12. tahrir. San-Paulu: Pearson Prentice Hall. 2007;74.

communication mechanisms³. Email, web forms, instant messaging, phone calls are the bank's means of communicating with customers.

Discussion. Communication in the banking industry can be seen by keeping in touch with valued customers, providing reliable information and services, and proactively communicating when any problem arises⁴. Bank communication is a tool for customers to express their needs, perspectives and opinions on the services provided by banks. If the bank professionalizes its communication, it will help customers to reduce technological, operational, functional costs, and solve their complaints faster⁵. Likewise, cross-selling of banking products can be a new area of customer engagement, helping to take the relationship between banks and customers to another level.

Customer relationship is one of the main indicators of bank profitability, so the attention of banks is gradually focused on customers through good communication⁶. Al-Qeed et al noted that banks today have begun to focus on and improve service quality with customers in mind. Service quality plays an important role in banking services banks and among customers and leads to high satisfaction,

³ Osiyo bankir. Chakana bank sohasida innovatsiyalar - Osiyo Tinch okeani; 2010.

⁴ Oly Ndubisi N, Kok Vah C. Munosabatlar marketingi va mijozlar ehtiyojini qondirish asoslarining omilli va diskriminant tahlillari. Intl. J. Bank Mrkt.2005;23(7):542-557.

⁵ Hoque ME, NMH. Nik Hoshim, Razzaque MA. Muloqot va moliyaviy muammolarning bank munosabatlariga ta'siri munosabatlar. Ser. Ind. J. 2018;38:13-14,1017-1042.

⁶ Bhat SA, Darzi MA. Customer relationship management: A review of Indian banking sector. The Bus. Rev. 2013;17(1-2):58-67.

loyalty to products and services⁷. Hartabeil and Saydam⁸ concluded that banking services strengthen customers' decision to stay with banks, and help them obtain additional advice and suggestions for improvement. The relationship between the bank and its client is a relationship between debtors and creditors, which is related to certain obligations, which distinguishes them from other ordinary debtors and creditors⁹. Devnarain et¹⁰ al argued that the relationship between banks and customers is created through a mutually agreed upon contract and that relationship is significant from the moment they open an account and ends immediately upon account closure.

Analysis and results. A bank connection is a communication method in which a customer uses technology to interact with their bank. It can be considered the equivalent of calling a bank, but instead of picking up the phone and talking to a bank representative, the customer can send messages and make transactions over

⁷ The impact of customer relationship management on achieving service quality of banking sector of Jordan. *Intl. J. of Bus. and Mgmt.* 2017;12(3):180-185.

⁸ Khartabiel MI, Saydam S. Banks employees satisfaction as a lead to customers satisfaction. *Intl. J. of Bus. and Soc. Sci.* 2014;5(9).

⁹ Dhman ZAZ. The effect of customer relationship management (crm) concept adoption on customer satisfactioncustomers perspective the case of coastal municipalities water utility cmwu-rafaah branch. MBA thesis, Dept. of Comm., Islamic Univ. of Gaza, Gaza, Palestine;2011.

¹⁰ Dewnarain S, Ramkissoon H, Mavondo F. Social customer relationship management: An integrated conceptual framework. *J. of Hosp. Mrkt. & Mgmt.* 2019;28(2):172-188.

the Internet. Banking communication can be used by financial institutions and their customers in two ways.

The first way to use a bank connection is for customers who want to contact their financial institution but don't want to use any kind of telephone connection. This may be due to privacy issues, disability, or reluctance to talk on the phone. Another reason may be that it is more convenient to communicate online rather than over the phone.

Today, there are many types of banking for businesses. They range from traditional marketing mailings, periodic mailings, and email updates to social media updates, video content, and even face-to-face meetings.

Importance of Banking Communication: Communication is the heart of banking. Communication is the lifeblood of a banking relationship. It is the connective tissue that keeps the bank in touch with its customers.

Vital reasons for the need for a bank connection:

- ✓ Some banks have mobile apps for customers who want to access their banking information and transactions on the go.
- ✓ check your bank account balance and transaction history and make online payments from anywhere with an internet connection.

When you lose this important connection, the bank risks losing its customers to competitors who value their relationship with them more than this bank.

Banking communication should be a two-way street to ensure that both parties are well informed. This allows customers to be aware of new products and services, as well as changes in the banking industry.

Reasons why banking relationships are important:

- ✓ First, most banks offer online banking services for their customers. With this service, the customer can easily check the bank account balance, transaction history and make online payment from anywhere with internet connection;

- ✓ Second, some banks have mobile apps for customers who want to access their banking information and transactions on the go;

Types of communication with customers. Banks have been using several types of tools as banking communication tools for quite some time. For most of us, banks are institutions that we take a bit of trust in and are generally viewed with a bit of skepticism.

Banks are known for protecting our personal information and bank transaction details and do not like to make them public.

Bank communication is mainly divided into two types:

1) Internal and other banking communications: Internal and other banking communications mean all types of documents, correspondence, presentations and other information materials used in the bank.

It includes all types of documents that bankers use to communicate with each other. These include e-mails, memos, reports, letters, etc., and banking communication refers to any type of interaction between customers and banks, whether internal or external banking. This includes website visits, internet banking visits and phone calls/sales calls.

2) Customer Communication: Customer communication is a major part of banking. It is the bank's way of communicating with its customers and building relationships with them. In fact, this is one of the most important aspects of banking, as it allows the bank to better understand its customers and provide them with more relevant information.

Customer communication is also an important means of making sure that all customers are satisfied with the bank's services. This helps the bank to improve customer retention, reduce customer complaints and increase overall satisfaction.

Popular customer communication channels in banking. Banks often use different methods to communicate with their customers. For example, they use email to communicate with customers every day. In addition to e-mail, banks often send

notices and other information by mail or e-mail. Communication channels with bank clients:

1. Live chat (Live chat). Customer communication channels have evolved rapidly over the past decade. Live chat is the most popular channel for communicating with customers. Online banking has become a popular channel for customers to approach their banks because it does not require their time and effort.

2. Chatbot. Chatbot is one of the latest customer communication tools used by banks to provide a wide range of services to their customers at any time of the day.

3. Call Center. The call center is an effective communication channel with customers in banking. This helps the bank to provide customer oriented services and helps in reducing the number of customer complaints. It also benefits customers by providing them with the information they need, which cannot be found on the internet.

4. Electronic mail (e-mail). E-mail is one of the simplest, most convenient and most effective means of banking communication. Banks use email as the main way to communicate with customers after social media.

5. Social networks. Banks are using social media to communicate with customers and increase their brand awareness. But is it really effective? Let's take a look at some statistics: 53% of consumers use social media to research products or services before making a purchase, and a staggering 49% of those surveyed say it's to find out if others have had a positive or negative experience with a brand. said The above are international opinions and standards on bank and customer communication channels. However, compared to the concept of bank and customer communication channels in Uzbekistan, such cases are considered as a simple way

of carrying out banking operations¹¹. Based on this, there are two types of this situation in the banking system of our country:

1. Traditional service;
2. Remote care.

Of course, the communication channel between the bank and the client in the traditional service is to visit the client's physical bank branch and carry out banking operations while communicating with the appropriate bank employee, which is a simple situation known to all of us.

However, the Central Bank divides the second view of this communication channel into the following categories:

Bank-Client is a computer-based system in which a special program is installed on the client's computer. This program stores all customer information (mainly payment documents and account statements) on the computer. A direct connection between the bank and the client's computer is made through a modem. Internet banking is a system that allows clients to manage their deposit accounts, including bank card accounts, via the Internet. This type of service is a system designed for making payments in real time while the client is connected to the bank remotely. The user accesses the system through a web browser. The Internet banking system is hosted on the bank's web server. The user has the opportunity to view all his information (payment documents and account statements) on the bank's website.

Mobile banking system is created on the basis of internet banking technology.

SMS-banking is a system of receiving information in the form of SMS to bank customers about transactions in their deposit accounts and accounts opened

¹¹ www.revechat.com

for bank cards. In order to receive information from the account, the client needs to send an SMS request to the bank's special phone number.

Nevertheless, the above are considered to be very standardized and can be said to be more of a way of bank transactions than a customer communication channel. Therefore, it is necessary for the banking system of Uzbekistan to study the experience of foreign countries and improve our own experience in the field of bank and customer communication channel, which we have emphasized at the beginning of this chapter.

Conclusion. In conclusion, we can see that the implementation of communication in banks can affect customer satisfaction. If banks do not follow the right communication strategies, the customer is more likely to become dissatisfied and switch banks. Banks need to adopt the right strategies and techniques to communicate properly with customers.

The way the bank communicates with customers depends on the structure and culture of the organization. Banks seem to be communicating well with customers, but customers still face problems in the flow of information on various issues from banks. Thus, banks must always put their customers first, because without customers, no bank can flourish and move forward by analyzing customer relationships through customer perception and communication techniques in banks.

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